

THE ZOO IS LOCATED IN THE CITY OF TERMIZ SURKHANDARYO REGION

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ABSTRACT: *The article talks about the role of cultural and educational centers, establishment of a zoo in the city of Termiz, existing species of animals, cooperation, reforms aimed at further development of the zoo in the city of Termiz. visit. was discussed. opinions are expressed and analyzed.*

Keywords: *cultural-educational center, zoo, breed, species, Red Book, cooperation, "Eng janubiy", YIMS, "Shitemir", local history museum, conservation, Euro-Asia, tourists.*

The 19th century French writer Victor Hugo said about the relationship between man, nature and animals: "It was necessary to civilize man in his relationship with another man. Now it is necessary to civilize man in relation to nature and animals." Friendship between humans and animals In order to establish relations, a zoo, which is a cultural and educational place, was established. they see wild and rare animals with their own eyes in order to leave and breed endangered animal breeds. They are raised in captivity or semi-captivity (in areas similar to nature) living conditions. Zoos existed in Egypt in 1500 BC. There are more than 720 zoos in the world. As of January 1, 2022, zoos operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan are located in Surkhandarya region, Fergana region and our capital, Tashkent. These zoos have 14,443 species of animals. The zoo, located in the city of Termiz, Surkhandarya region, was established in 1934 in the local history museum. After the number of animals increased, it was established

in 1939 on a 35-hectare area next to the Surkhondarya Museum of Local History. In 1942, the zoo was closed and its animals were transferred to the Tashkent city zoo. Work began on May 1, 1947. In 2001, Termiz Zoo was rebuilt in accordance with international standards. A 1979 documentary called " Eng janubiy " was made about this zoo. The zoo has 112 species, 766 animals, 24 species of animals included in the "Qizil kitob" and 16 species of birds. 77 employees carry out their work activities. 2 veterinarians and 2 paramedics take care of animal health for rare animals. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 30, 2021 "On measures to accelerate afforestation in the Republic, more effective organization of tree protection" PF-46 and 2022 02 RA-1-18233 dated October 30, 561 pieces of fruit in the Termiz Zoo in order to ensure the implementation of the letter of assignment No. 02- RA-1-18233 and to ensure the implementation of "Dolzarb - 40 days" during the autumn planting season and ornamental tree saplings were planted, barley, blue clover, green (zelen), wheat, onion products were planted on the auxiliary farm land located in "Jaironkhona" massif, Termiz district, and additional feed for these animals maintained as Bird Day on April 1 and Tiger Day on July 29 are widely celebrated in Termiz Zoo. Animals are divided into 4 sections:

1. Department of ungulates.
2. Department of predators.
3. Department of birds.
4. Department of reptiles.

In the ungulate department, the number of Central Asian goats increased by 6 heads, Yoldor sheep by 1 head, Morkhor by 1 head, and Mountain sheep by 2 heads during 12 months. 2 wild boars were brought as patronage.

The number of African lions increased by 2 heads and Himalayan bears by 1 head during 12 months in the department of predators.

In the poultry section, Ukki for 1 head, Phoenix chicken for 3 heads, Pakana chicken for 3 heads, Bentham chicken for 4 heads, White-headed Kumai for 1 head, Indutka

for 16 heads, Cesarka for 3 heads, Kryakova chicken for 5 heads for 12 months increased.

In the department of reptiles, domestic rabbits fed on a daily basis increased by 10 heads. These will certainly prevent further expansion of the zoo and species of animals. The territory is neat, the surroundings are filled with beautiful and fruit trees and flowers that give pleasure to people. The entrance to the zoo attracts the attention of a person who has visited the zoo and evokes a good mood, cultural entertainment and great impressions. Everything in the zoo is designed for the comfort of the animals, the cages are made of nylon mesh to prevent the birds from hitting the metal fences. Children can walk around with their parents whenever they want, have fun and at the same time get interesting information about the animals of zoos around the world.

"Qizil kitob" is a book of danger and hope. It is a state document that records rare species of plants and animals that are disappearing or in danger of disappearing. There are two reasons for the disappearance of animal breeds and plant species on earth; the first reason is the result of changes in natural conditions, and the second reason is the result of anthropogenic human actions. A lot of practical work is being done to protect the animal and plant world, taking into account them, each state, region and region is organizing its own Qizil kitob. The pages of "Qizil kitob" are never finished, its pages are constantly filled with new species of plants and animals. In order to shorten the pages of the " Qizil kitob ", it is necessary to constantly increase human culture and behavior, this is one of the important problems that scientists face. For this purpose, zoos are established to increase people's knowledge about animals. To appreciate everything, it is necessary to preserve even a living creature that is wonderful in nature. In the international " Qizil kitob ": " Qizil kitob is a document, it is the conscience of a person. Every nation has the responsibility to protect its natural resources before the world".

From March 27 to April 2, 2022, B. Jumayev, the chief zootechnician of the Termiz city zoo, participated in the international seminar held by YIMS "International Zoological Information System" at the Tashkent Zoo and received an international

certificate. According to the results of the seminar, it was planned to establish cooperation relations with the Termiz Zoo. On April 18-20 of this year, Professor Batirkhanov Marhabat Serigbayev, chairman of the board of "Shitemir" company, doctor of veterinary sciences, from Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan, visited as a guest. The goal was to breed and preserve unique species of animals in the zoo. At the end of the visit, cooperation relations were established with "Shitemir" company. In November 2022, Termiz Zoo became a full member of the Association of Euro-Asian Zoos and Aquariums.

In conclusion, it should be said that cooperative relations are one of the big steps towards turning the zoo into one of the world's leading zoos, animal exchange, and establishing cultural ties with independent countries. Caring for nature is humanity's own care, because man is a child of nature. Damage to nature is man's own damage. The diversity of our mother nature did not appear yesterday or today, but this priceless gift is a priceless legacy left to us by our ancestors for thousands of years. That is why each of us should feel responsible and responsible for the protection of natural resources and protect it like the apple of an eye. According to the conclusion of the visit, the following measures should be implemented in order to further develop the zoo and increase the number of foreign tourists:

- active advertising on social networks by making videos about the zoo;
- creation of souvenirs and figurines reminiscent of the Termiz zoo at a glance;
- carrying information boards in three languages;
- creating an opportunity for guests arriving in different weather conditions; covered seats, shelter from rain.

As a result of these reforms, the Termiz Zoo will expand, and the number of tourists and residents who come to establish cooperative relations will increase.

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